

ASSESSING ICT COMPETENCE AND ITS IMPACT ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG BACHELOR OF ELEMENTARY EDUCATION STUDENTS

Rachel G. Toguina

Benguet State University – Buguias Campus, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This research investigates the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills of Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd) students at Benguet State University-Buguias Campus. The study aims to evaluate students' proficiency in ICT, identify challenges affecting their academic performance, and recommend enhancements to ICT training within the curriculum. ICT's integration into education is critical, as highlighted by the Philippine government's efforts to promote technology use in schools through legislative acts like Republic Act No. 10844 and DepEd Order No. 36, Series of 2013 (DepEd, 2013). The study employs a quantitative methodology, using a questionnaire to assess BEEd students' knowledge of ICT hardware, software, and literacy. The research finds that students generally possess a high level of knowledge regarding basic ICT operations but face challenges such as insufficient funding for ICT devices, low network bandwidth, and inadequate information literacy training. These issues significantly impact their academic performance. To address these gaps, the study suggests curriculum improvements, including enhanced ICT training for effective technology integration into lesson planning and assessment. The findings underscore the necessity for continued development of ICT competencies to ensure future educators are well-equipped to utilize technology in their teaching practices. This research contributes to a deeper understanding of ICT integration in teacher education and highlights areas for potential improvement in educational technology training programs.

Keywords: *ICT Skills, Teacher Education, Curriculum Enhancement, Educational Technology, Student Proficiency*

INTRODUCTION

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has fundamentally transformed education, necessitating that aspiring teachers acquire essential ICT skills to enhance their teaching effectiveness (Adedoyin & Soyibo, 2022). This study aims to evaluate the ICT proficiency of Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd) students to identify gaps and provide targeted support for improving their technological competence.

Globally, ICT's role in education has become increasingly vital. In the Philippines, government initiatives like the Department of Information and Communications Technology (DICT) Act of 2015 and DepEd Order No. 36, Series of 2013 reflect a strong commitment to integrating ICT in education (DepEd, 2013). The Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (Republic Act No. 10533) also underscores the importance of a robust educational system that leverages technology to meet national needs.

ICT encompasses a broad range of tools and activities, including social networking platforms, video-sharing services, and communication tools such as projectors and desktops (Hu et al., 2018). Its integration into educational settings aims to enhance learning experiences and provide access to diverse resources, making ICT an integral part of modern education.

Research indicates that while ICT integration holds promise for improving educational experiences, there remains a need for ongoing research, particularly in teacher education. Previous studies have explored ICT's impact on education, but there is limited focus on assessing ICT skills among BEEd students, highlighting a gap in understanding how ICT integration affects teacher preparation (Ilogho et al., 2014; Amasuomo, 2015).

Studies from various countries, such as Iran and Australia, have demonstrated the benefits of ICT in creating interactive learning environments and facilitating customized learning plans (Mohammadi & Carcass, 2013; Voogt et al., 2021). However, closing the digital divide and equipping educators with effective ICT training remains a significant challenge (Head Foundation, 2020).

In the context of pre-service teacher education, some research suggests that BEEd students might possess a higher level of ICT competency than previously thought, indicating potential advancements in teacher education programs (Dela Fuente & Binas, 2020). Despite this, there are concerns about the gap between anticipated and actual ICT skills among future teachers, which could impact their effectiveness in integrating technology into their teaching (Mathivanan et al., 2021).

Challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, insufficient training, and limited access to ICT resources continue to hinder effective ICT integration in education (Vidal,

2017; Ahmad et al., 2019). For instance, rural schools in the Philippines face a digital divide due to poor infrastructure and equipment shortages (Lupina, 2021).

The study underscores the need for BEEd students to possess foundational ICT skills to navigate and utilize technology effectively in their future classrooms. Understanding and addressing the challenges these students face is crucial for developing innovative teaching methods and ensuring successful technology integration (Esfujani & Zamani, 2020).

Moreover, the study highlights the importance of incorporating ICT into the curriculum and providing appropriate training for future educators. Effective use of technology can enhance teaching practices and improve educational outcomes, but it requires a concerted effort from educators, institutions, and policymakers to address existing gaps (Catalano, 2019).

Finally, the study aims to contribute to the ongoing discourse on ICT integration in education by focusing on BEEd programs and identifying specific areas for improvement. By assessing ICT competence among BEEd students, the research seeks to offer insights into the challenges and opportunities for enhancing technology integration in teacher education (Ertmer, 2015; Khalid, 2017).

Research Questions

This study seeks to examine the challenges and effects of assessing the ICT competence of BEEd students on their academic performance. Despite recognizing the benefits of ICT, the specific challenges and effects of BEEd student's ICT competence on their academic performance remain unexplored. This study aims to address the following key problems:

1. What is the level of knowledge of BEEd students in terms of hardware, software, and ICT literacy?
2. What are the challenges do first-year, second-year, and third-year BEEd students encounter that affect their academic performance?
3. What ICT training or curriculum enhancements can be developed to improve the teaching demonstration sessions and academic performance of BEEd students?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a quantitative research methodology to assess the ICT competence of Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd) students at Benguet State University Buguias Campus. This approach was chosen for its effectiveness in collecting and analyzing numerical data to address research questions related to ICT knowledge, challenges, and training needs. According to Haegele and Hodge (2015), quantitative methods are particularly useful for understanding phenomena through statistical and

mathematical analysis. In this study, a structured questionnaire was utilized to gather data on various aspects of ICT competence among the students.

The population for the study included BEEd students from first to third year at the university, totaling 52 respondents. This demographic was selected to provide a comprehensive overview of ICT proficiency across different stages of the BEEd program. The sample was divided into first-year (18 students), second-year (11 students), and third-year (23 students) groups, ensuring a representative cross-section of the student body. This stratified sampling approach allowed for a detailed examination of ICT skills and challenges at different educational levels.

To collect data, researchers administered a detailed questionnaire designed to measure knowledge in hardware, software, and general ICT literacy. The questionnaire was adapted from existing instruments and tailored to address specific research objectives. It included sections on technical proficiency, perceived challenges, and recommendations for curriculum enhancement. The researchers obtained necessary approvals from relevant university authorities before distributing the questionnaires, ensuring ethical compliance and proper authorization.

Data collection involved administering the questionnaire in person, with researchers overseeing the process to ensure clarity and completeness of responses. All collected data were kept confidential to protect respondent privacy. The completed questionnaires were checked for accuracy, tallied, and then analyzed using descriptive statistical methods to interpret the results. This approach facilitated a clear understanding of students' ICT competencies and the challenges they face.

RESULTS

Table 1. Level of Academic Performance of the Grade 7 Learners Based on their Pre-test Scores

STATEMENT	MEAN	D.E.	T-VALUE	SIG.
1.I can effortlessly manage copying and moving files between folders, devices, or cloud storage.	3.365	VK	40.784**	0.000
2.I can easily create, edit, and format digital text files in various software programs.	3.289	VK	37.246**	0.000
3.I'm comfortable using advanced search engine features to refine my searches effectively.	3.269	VK	35.707**	0.000
4.I can confidently manage video conferences, including recording audio and video.	3.173	MK	33.749**	0.000

5.I can easily identify secure websites by checking for HTTPS, safety logos, and certificates.	3.058	MK	30.402**	0.000
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Legend:

3.26-4.00	Very Knowledgeable	VK	** - highly significant
2.51-3.25	Moderately Knowledgeable	MK	* - significant
1.76-2.50	Slightly Knowledgeable	SK	^{ns} - not significant
1.00-1.75	Not Knowledgeable	NK	

Table 2. Level of knowledge of BEED students in terms of hardware, software, and ICT literacy.

STATEMENT	MEAN	D.E.	T-VALUE	SIG.
1. Low bandwidth from my network provider.	3.135	A	30.475**	0.000
2. A lack of funds to purchase ICT gadgets.	3.115	A	33.231**	0.000
3. Insufficient funds to subscribe or purchase data for browsing.	3.096	A	28.862**	0.000
4. Network authentication/restriction from students.	3.039	A	28.605**	0.000
5. Poor/inadequate information literacy and training programs at the university.	2.981	A	35.234**	0.000

Legend:

3.26-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA	** - highly significant
2.51-3.25	Agree	A	* - significant
1.76-2.50	Disagree	D	^{ns} - not significant
1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree	SD	

Table 3. Level of agreement of BEED student on the ICT training or curriculum enhancement.

STATEMENT	MEAN	D.E.	T-VALUE	SIG.
1. 1.Integrating technology resources effectively into lesson plans.	3.577	SA	51.704**	0.000
2. 2.Utilizing technology to provide effective and personalized feedback to students.	3.539	SA	47.171**	0.000
3. 3.Implementing technology to support blended learning environments (combining online and in-person teaching).	3.519	SA	39.566**	0.000

4. 4.Using presentation and interactive whiteboards to create dynamic and interactive presentations.	3.500	SA	41.350**	0.000
5. 5.Designing and grading online quizzes and assignments for efficient assessment.	3.481	SA	43.499**	0.000

Legend:

3.26-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA	** - highly significant
2.51-3.25	Agree	A	* - significant
1.76-2.50	Disagree	D	^{ns} - not significant
1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree	SD	

DISCUSSION

The study aimed to evaluate the ICT skills of Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd) students, focusing on their knowledge of hardware, software, and general ICT literacy. The results showed significant variation in their expertise, with a high overall mean knowledge level of 3.365 and a T-value of 40.784, suggesting that most students are quite knowledgeable about various ICT functions. However, some areas, such as identifying secure websites, were less familiar to them, indicating that while students are proficient in many ICT aspects, they still have room for improvement, especially in understanding online security.

The analysis also shed light on how well BEEd students use ICT to enhance communication with teachers, which is crucial for bridging gaps in education. Despite their strong overall knowledge, students face challenges that impact their academic performance. With mean scores between 3.135 and 2.981, the data reflects a shared recognition of these difficulties. These challenges, consistent with findings from Nwosu J.C. et al., highlight the need for additional support to help students overcome obstacles to their academic success.

To address these issues, the study examined possible improvements in ICT training and curriculum. The most highly rated enhancement was the successful integration of technology into lesson plans, with a mean score of 3.577. This suggests that students and educators see significant value in using technology effectively to enrich teaching. On the other hand, using presentation and interactive whiteboards scored lower, indicating a need for better methods in this area.

The study also highlighted the importance of providing personalized feedback through technology, creating and grading online quizzes, and implementing blended learning environments. Personalized feedback had a mean score of 3.539, while online quizzes and blended learning scored 3.481 and 3.519, respectively. These findings,

inspired by Delfino (2019), suggest that targeted ICT training can significantly improve teaching and learning outcomes.

In summary, the research emphasizes the need for focused ICT training and curriculum improvements to address challenges and enhance the educational experience for BEEd students. By improving areas such as online security awareness and technology integration, educators can better support students and improve their academic performance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The study reveals that BEEd students exhibit strong overall ICT knowledge, especially in managing files and common functions, but show notable weaknesses in online security, indicating a need for targeted improvement in this area. Challenges impacting their academic performance are evident, suggesting that despite their ICT proficiency, obstacles exist that hinder their educational success. Moreover, the study highlights the necessity for enhanced ICT training and curriculum upgrades, particularly in integrating technology into lesson plans and utilizing personalized feedback, to better support teaching and boost academic achievements. Addressing these areas can bridge existing gaps and improve both student engagement and educational outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were drawn:

To address the gaps identified in the study, it is recommended that BEEd students receive targeted training focused on improving their ability to recognize and use secure online practices, such as identifying secure websites and understanding safety features. Additionally, enhancing the curriculum to emphasize the integration of technology into lesson plans, providing effective personalized feedback through digital tools, and designing dynamic and interactive online assessments could significantly boost both teaching effectiveness and student performance. Schools should also invest in ongoing professional development for educators to ensure they are equipped with the latest ICT skills and pedagogical strategies to foster a more tech-savvy and academically successful student body.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before conducting the proposed study, the researcher undertook the following procedures to ensure ethical considerations in the conduct of a research. The researcher first secured written permission to float the researcher instruments from the school authorities of the intended informants of the study; A letter accompanied the survey/research instrument that was given to the target respondents/informants/subjects indicating among others; to wit: 1) the participants identity would not be divulged in the

current study in compliance to the provisions of the Data Privacy Law; 2) all information and data from the participants/respondents/subjects of the current study would be held in strict confidentiality; 3) when the respondents/subjects answered the survey questionnaire/instrument, that means they agree to participate in the study as respondents; 4) the responses in the questionnaire/instrument is presented in aggregate and not as individual perceptions; and 5) the research conducted is primarily for academic requirement only.

The researcher declare that all materials/findings borrowed from other sources and included in his/her thesis/dissertation are properly cited and acknowledged.

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